

Title: Evidence-based Cesarean safety clinical protocol

Authors: Chi Chiung Grace Chen;¹ Stephen Rulisa,² Alison M. El Ayadi³

Affiliations

¹Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics, Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, MD USA

²Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, University of Rwanda, Kigali, Rwanda

³Department of Obstetrics, Gynecology and Reproductive Sciences, University of California, San Francisco, San Francisco CA USA

Background

Surgical site infection (SSI) following cesarean section (CS) is the most common healthcare-associated infection in Sub-Saharan Africa, despite being largely preventable. As low and middle-income countries (LMIC) rapidly expand emergency obstetric services, post-CS SSI is rising and represents a substantial cause of maternal morbidity. In countries such as Rwanda, incidence is as high as 26%. In contrast, baseline rates in well-resourced countries are 6-8%; and evidence-based interventions may reduce SSI to 1-2%. Our team of US and Rwandan investigators has developed a CS safety bundle of implementation strategies composed of peer mentorship, pre-CS huddle, safe surgery checklist and training in an evidence-based clinical practice protocol shown to reduce CS-related SSI infection in high-resource settings. These implementation strategies are intended support evidence-based practice, reducing maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality. Components of the evidence-based practice protocol were identified on systematic review of the literature and are detailed in the table below.

Evidence-based Cesarean safety clinical protocol components

Component	Description	Rationale
Preoperative considerations		
Patient bathing	Preoperative full body bathing (shower or bath) with soap (antimicrobial or nonantimicrobial) the day prior to or the day of surgery	WHO and CDC recommend patient bathe or shower the night before or the day of surgery using either plain or antimicrobial soap. ¹ Systematic review demonstrated no significant reduction in SSI rates when comparing bathing with plain or chlorhexidine soap (OR 0.92, 95%CI 0.80-1.04) ²
Intraoperative considerations: general procedures		
Hair removal	Preoperative hair removal discouraged.	Meta-analysis found clipping and no hair removal was associated with a significantly lower risk of SSI compared to shaving (OR 0.51, 95%CI 0.34-0.78). ²
Abdominal skin preparation	Prepare abdominal skin with chlorhexidine gluconate 2% w/v isopropyl alcohol 70% v/v (CHG), let area to dry for at least 3 minutes.	CHG has been found to be superior to povidone-iodine for preventing SSI after clean-contaminated surgery and CS ³ : (RR 0.59, 95%CI 0.41-0.85), ⁴ (RR 0.72, 95% CI 0.52-0.98). ⁵ The WHO and CDC recommend use of alcohol-based skin preparation for the prevention of SSI. ^{1,2} CHG can be locally produced in African Hospitals, ² and is cost-effective given the reduction in SSI. ⁶
Vaginal preparation	Prepare vagina with 10% povidone-iodine for 30 seconds.	Meta-analysis identified reduced risk of postoperative infections with 10% povidone-iodine vaginal scrubbing immediately before CS: endometritis (RR 0.52, 95%CI 0.37-0.72) and fever (RR 0.65, 95%CI 0.50-0.86). ⁷
Prophylactic antibiotics	Administer within 60 minutes of CS and before skin incision. <u>Unlabored</u> : Cefazolin or Clindamycin + Gentamicin if penicillin allergy ⁸ . <u>Labored</u> : Cefazolin + Azithromycin ^{10,9} Exact antibiotic regimen will depend on availability and local guidelines. No continuation of antibiotics postoperatively. ¹	Meta-analysis found reduced incidences of CS associated febrile morbidity: wound infection (RR 0.40, 95%CI 0.35-0.46), endometritis (RR 0.38, 95%CI 0.34-0.42) and serious maternal infectious complications (RR 0.31, 95%CI 0.20-0.49). ⁹ Systematic review found no additional benefit in reducing SSI with prolonged postoperative antibiotic use compared with single dose prophylaxis (OR 0.89, 95%CI 0.77-1.03). ¹²
Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH)	Administer oxytocin or carbetocin (if oxytocin is not available). If hemorrhage continues, add agents such as ergometrine, misoprostol, or tranexamic depending on availability.	Oxytocin bolus plus infusion has been shown to decrease the need for additional uterotonics (OR 0.61, 95%CI 0.48-0.78). ¹⁰ Oxytocin and carbetocin alone has been shown to decrease PPH (≥ 500 mL: RR 0.58, 95%CI 0.49-0.70; RR 0.72, 95% CI 0.56-0.93, respectively; ≥ 1000 mL: RR 0.59, 95%CI 0.50-0.70; RR 0.87 95%CI 0.62-1.21, respectively). ¹¹ Ergometrine with oxytocin and misoprostol with oxytocin have also been shown to decrease PPH compared with oxytocin alone (≥ 500 mL: RR 0.70 95%CI 0.59-0.84; RR 0.70 95%CI 0.58-0.86, respectively; ≥ 1000 mL: RR 0.83, 95%CI 0.66-1.03; RR 0.88 95%CI 0.70-1.11, respectively). Tranexamic acid has been shown to significantly reduce death from bleeding when administered within 3 hours of the inciting event (RR 0.69, 95%CI 0.52-0.91). ¹² and is recommended for use by the WHO.
Foley catheter placement	Bladder catheter placement (Foley) prior to CS with removal after CS. For patients with suspected prolonged active labor, prolong bladder drainage may be continued for the duration of hospitalization and for up to 14 days postoperatively.	Foley catheter placement during CS has not been found to be associated with improved outcomes; ^{13,14} however, the USAID-supported Fistula Care project recommends catheter placement in patients undergoing CS and prolonged bladder drainage of ≥ 14 days in patients with prolonged active labor with removal of catheter after 14 days if no evidence of bladder injury. ¹⁵
Intraoperative considerations: operative techniques		
Skin incision	Use Joel Cohen (JC) skin incision.	JC compared with Pfannenstiel skin incision is associated with less blood loss (-64.4 mL, 95%CI -91.3, -37.6), operative time (-18.6 minutes, 95%CI -24.8, -12.5), and fever (RR 0.47, 95%CI 0.28-0.81). ¹⁶
Bladder Flap	Develop a bladder flap (opening the visceral peritoneum between the uterus and bladder with dissection of the bladder off the lower uterine segment) prior to the hysterotomy, and not closed after hysterotomy closure.	One RCT (n=258) showed a decrease in median time to hysterotomy in the non-bladder flap group (9 vs 10 minutes, p=0.04) with no differences in other perioperative outcomes (e.g., total operative time, blood loss, pain, UTI, endometritis) suggesting that creating a bladder flap may not improve outcomes. ¹⁷ However, only 20% of the patients underwent CS for failure to progress. In our settings, most patients will be undergoing CS for failure to progress as most CS are not elective; if the bladder is dissected away from the lower uterine segment prior to the hysterotomy incision, theoretically the surgeon may be less likely to incise into the bladder.
Hysterotomy site	Create the hysterotomy approximately 6cm cephalad of the pubic bone (approximately 3-4 fingerbreadths above the pubic bone).	Most CS in our setting will be performed for failure to progress, where the labored lower uterine segment may be thinner. Making the hysterotomy incision higher in the lower uterine segment may prevent unintended hysterotomy extensions and bladder injury. A case-control study found a transverse incision in the upper part of the lower uterine demonstrated lower blood loss (198 mL, 95% CI 137.9-258.1, vs 330.1 mL, 95% CI 261.6-398.6; p<0.05), reduced operation time (30.5 minutes, 95% CI 23.9-37.1, vs 45.3 minutes, 95% CI 38.1-52.5; p<0.05), and fewer torn incisions (0 vs 8; p<0.05) compared to the traditional lower uterine segment incision. ¹⁸

Hysterotomy extension	Extend hysterotomy bluntly (using fingers) in a cephalad-caudal direction.	One RCT demonstrated significantly less intraoperative blood loss with the use of blunt vs. sharp hysterotomy extension (375 vs. 443 mL, p=0.001). ¹⁹ A meta-analysis comparing blunt dissection in the transverse direction vs. the cephalad-caudal direction showed significantly less unintended hysterotomy extensions (8.9% vs. 4.8%) and decreased rates of blood loss (>1500 mL) (1.7% vs. 0.2%) in the cephalad-caudal group. ²⁰
Placental delivery	Deliver placenta with cord traction followed by manual sweep with laparotomy sponge to remove placental fragments/debris.	Compared with cord traction, manual placental removal has been found to increase rates of endometritis (RR 1.64, 95%CI 1.42-1.90), blood loss at time of delivery (+94.4mL 95%CI 17.2-171.6), and the duration of hospital stay (0.39 days 95%CI 0.17-0.61). ²¹
Hysterotomy closure	Close the hysterectomy using a double layered closure: first layer in a continuous, non-locking fashion; second layer in a continuous, locking fashion.	A meta-analysis found single layer, continuous, non-locking closure compared with a double layer closure resulted in a higher risk of uterine rupture (OR 4.96, 95%CI 2.58-9.52). ²² Double layer closure was associated with thicker lower urine segment (+0.11mm, 95%CI 0.02-0.21) and decreased risk of scar dehiscence on subsequent deliveries that required CS (trial of labor: 3.2 vs 10.7%, p<0.001; no labor 1.6 vs 4.0%, p=0.046). ²³ During a double layer closure, there is sonographic evidence of better myometrial healing when the first layer is not locked. ²⁴
Parietal peritoneum	No closure of the parietal peritoneum	Evidence is insufficient that closure of the peritoneum would justify the additional operative time and suture cost. ²⁵
Subcutaneous tissue and skin closure	Close the subcutaneous tissue, if the tissue is >2cm in depth, in a running, non-locking fashion. Close the skin with suture in subcuticular fashion.	A meta-analysis found a 34% (95%CI 9%-52%) decrease in wound disruption with subcutaneous closure (RR 0.66, 95%CI 0.48-0.91) in women with subcutaneous tissue of >2cm. ²⁶ With other evidence-based techniques (chlorhexidine skin antisepsis, prophylactic antibiotics), this practice has also been found to lower the risk of wound complications including SSI, cellulitis, seroma, hematoma and separation (RR 0.75, 95%CI 0.58-0.95). ²⁷ A meta-analysis demonstrated less wound complications with skin closure with suture as opposed to staples (RR 0.49, 95%CI 0.28-0.87), largely attributed to lower incidence of wound separation with no significant difference in infection risk. ^{28,29}
Postoperative considerations		
Incisional care	Remove incisional dressing 48 hours after CS. Inspect incision and examine abdomen daily during hospitalization and prior to discharge from hospital.	Evidence is insufficient to support the prolong use of postoperative incisional dressing or the use of a specific type of dressing after clean surgery or clean-contaminated surgery. ³⁰ Following clean surgery, the risk of SSI: basic wound contact dressings vs. none (exposed incision) (RR 0.37, 95%CI 0.04-3.46), transparent film dressings vs. none (RR 0.20, 95%CI 0.02-1.69), silver-containing dressings vs. none (RR 8.0, 95%CI 1.02-62.55.), transparent film dressings vs. basic wound contact dressings, (RR 1.34, 95%CI 0.70-2.55); hydrocolloid dressings vs. basic wound contact dressings (RR 0.91, 95% CI 0.30-2.78); silver-containing dressings vs. basic wound contact dressings (RR 1.11, 95%CI 0.47-2.62). Following potentially contaminated surgery, risk of SSI: basic wound contact dressings vs. none (RR 1.34, 95%CI 0.82-2.19), hydrocolloid dressings vs. basic wound contact dressings (RR 0.57, 95%CI 0.22-1.51); silver-containing dressings vs. basic wound contact dressings (RR 0.83, 95%CI 0.51-1.37). A meta-analysis found that there is an increased risk of venous thromboembolism (VTE) following CS as compared to vaginal delivery (OR 3.7, 95%CI 3.0-4.6), however, the overall incidence of VTE is low (approximately 3 per 1000 patients). ³² A Cochrane review found that there was no statistically significant difference in symptomatic thromboembolic events when comparing heparin prophylaxis with placebo (RR 1.3, 95%CI 0.39-4.27), however no trial compared pharmacological with mechanical prophylaxis. ³³
Thromboprophylaxis	Use pneumatic compression devices routinely throughout hospitalization until patient is fully ambulatory. Decision to use additional pharmacological prophylaxis (e.g. low molecular weight heparin) should account for individual thromboembolic risk ³¹	
Patient discharge instructions and follow-up	Administer daily wound monitoring / care instructions at the time of discharge. After discharge, conduct weekly telephone monitoring, with in-person visit at 4 weeks post-CS.	Although there is limited evidence to support the efficacy of offering specific patient discharge instructions on patient outcomes, it is reasonable to offer patients postoperative educational resources that can be easily understood. ³⁴ The American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists recommend that all women have contact with a healthcare provider within 3 weeks of delivery and a postpartum visit within 12 weeks. ^{35,36}

SSI: surgical site infection; WHO: World Health Organization; LMIC: low and middle-income countries; CDC: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention; OR: odds ratio; RR: relative risk; CI: confidence interval; RCT: randomized controlled trial; UTI: urinary tract infection; ERAS: enhanced recovery after surgery. Enhanced recovery after surgery (ERAS) recommendations, not otherwise mentioned, throughout the perioperative period including anesthesia medications, diet, thromboprophylaxis, fluid management, analgesia, nutritional care and glycemic control, and early mobilization will be followed when possible.^{26,37,38}

References

- Berrios-Torres SI, Umscheid CA, Bratzler DW, et al. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention Guideline for the Prevention of Surgical Site Infection, 2017. *JAMA surgery* 2017; **152**(8): 784-91.
- World Health Organization. Global Guidelines for the Prevention of Surgical Site Infection. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2016.
- Amer-Alshiek J, Alshiek T, Almog B, et al. Can we reduce the surgical site infection rate in cesarean sections using a chlorhexidine-based antisepsis protocol? *The journal of maternal-fetal & neonatal medicine : the official journal of the European Association of Perinatal Medicine, the Federation of Asia and Oceania Perinatal Societies, the International Society of Perinatal Obstetricians* 2013; **26**(17): 1749-52.
- Darouiche RO, Wall MJ, Jr., Itani KMF, et al. Chlorhexidine-Alcohol versus Povidone-Iodine for Surgical-Site Antisepsis. *The New England journal of medicine* 2010; **362**(1): 18-26.
- Tolcher MC, Whitham MD, El-Nashar SA, Clark SL. Chlorhexidine-Alcohol Compared with Povidone-Iodine Preoperative Skin Antisepsis for Cesarean Delivery: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Am J Perinatol* 2019; **36**(2): 118-23.
- Lee I, Agarwal RK, Lee BY, Fishman NO, Umscheid CA. Systematic review and cost analysis comparing use of chlorhexidine with use of iodine for preoperative skin antisepsis to prevent surgical site infection. *Infection control and hospital epidemiology* 2010; **31**(12): 1219-29.
- Caissutti C, Saccone G, Zullo F, et al. Vaginal Cleansing Before Cesarean Delivery: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Obstetrics and gynecology* 2017; **130**(3): 527-38.
- ACOG Practice Bulletin No. 199: Use of Prophylactic Antibiotics in Labor and Delivery. *Obstetrics and gynecology* 2018; **132**(3): e103-e19.
- Small FM, Grivell RM. Antibiotic prophylaxis versus no prophylaxis for preventing infection after cesarean section. *The Cochrane database of systematic reviews* 2014; (10): CD007482-CD.

10. Sheehan SR, Montgomery AA, Carey M, et al. Oxytocin bolus versus oxytocin bolus and infusion for control of blood loss at elective caesarean section: double blind, placebo controlled, randomised trial. *BMJ (Clinical research ed)* 2011; **343**: d4661-d.
11. Gallos ID, Williams HM, Price MJ, et al. Uterotonic agents for preventing postpartum haemorrhage: a network meta-analysis. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2018; **4**(4): Cd011689. PMC6494487
12. Woman Trial Collaborators. Effect of early tranexamic acid administration on mortality, hysterectomy, and other morbidities in women with post-partum haemorrhage (WOMAN): an international, randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet (London, England)* 2017; **389**(10084): 2105-16.
13. Li L, Wen J, Wang L, Li YP, Li Y. Is routine indwelling catheterisation of the bladder for caesarean section necessary? A systematic review. *BJOG : an international journal of obstetrics and gynaecology* 2011; **118**(4): 400-9.
14. Oliphant SS, Bochenska K, Tolge ME, Catov JM, Zyczynski HM. Maternal lower urinary tract injury at the time of Cesarean delivery. *International Urogynecology Journal* 2014; **25**(12): 1709-14.
15. Fistula Care. Urinary Catheterization for Primary and Secondary Prevention of Obstetric Fistula: Report of a Consultative Meeting to Review and Standardize Current Guidelines and Practices, March 13-15 at the Sheraton Hotel, Abuja, Nigeria. New York, NY: EngenderHealth/Fistula Care, 2013.
16. Hofmeyr JG, Novikova N, Mathai M, Shah A. Techniques for cesarean section. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* 2009; **201**(5): 431-44.
17. Tuuli MG, Odibo AO, Fogertey P, Roehl K, Stamilio D, Macones GA. Utility of the Bladder Flap at Cesarean Delivery. *Obstetrics & Gynecology* 2012; **119**(4): 815-21.
18. Shao Y, Pradhan M. Higher Incision at Upper Part of Lower Segment Cesarean Section. *JNMA J Nepal Med Assoc* 2014; **52**(194): 764-70.
19. Sekhavat L, Dehghani Firouzabadi R, Mojiri P. Effect of expansion technique of uterine incision on maternal blood loss in cesarean section. *Archives of Gynecology and Obstetrics* 2009; **282**(5): 475-9.
20. Xodo S, Saccone G, Cromi A, Ozcan P, Spagnolo E, Berghella V. Cephalad-caudad versus transverse blunt expansion of the low transverse uterine incision during cesarean delivery. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol* 2016; **202**: 75-80.
21. Anorlu R, Maholwana B. Methods of delivering the placenta at caesarean section. The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd; 2004.
22. Roberge S, Chaillet N, Boutin A, et al. Single- versus double-layer closure of the hysterotomy incision during cesarean delivery and risk of uterine rupture. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics* 2011; **115**(1): 5-10.
23. Vachon-Marceau C, Demers S, Bujold E, et al. Single versus double-layer uterine closure at cesarean: impact on lower uterine segment thickness at next pregnancy. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* 2017; **217**(1): 65.e1-.e5.
24. Roberge S, Demers S, Girard M, et al. Impact of uterine closure on residual myometrial thickness after cesarean: a randomized controlled trial. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* 2016; **214**(4): 507.e1-.e6.
25. Bamigboye AA, Hofmeyr GJ. Closure versus non-closure of the peritoneum at caesarean section: short- and long-term outcomes. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 2014; **Aug 11**.
26. Chelmow D, Rodriguez EJ, Sabatini MM. Suture closure of subcutaneous fat and wound disruption after cesarean delivery: a meta-analysis. *Obstetrics and gynecology* 2004; **103**(5 Pt 1): 974-80.
27. Temming LA, Raghuraman N, Carter EB, et al. Impact of evidence-based interventions on wound complications after cesarean delivery. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* 2017; **217**(4): 449.e1-.e9. PMC5614824
28. Caughey AB, Wood SL, Macones GA, et al. Guidelines for intraoperative care in cesarean delivery: Enhanced Recovery After Surgery Society Recommendations (Part 2). *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* 2018; **219**(6): 533-44.
29. Mackeen AD, Schuster M, Berghella V. Suture versus staples for skin closure after cesarean: a metaanalysis. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* 2015; **212**(5): 621.e1-10.
30. Dumville JC, Gray TA, Walter CJ, et al. Dressings for the prevention of surgical site infection. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2016; **12**(12): Cd003091. PMC6464019
31. ACOG Practice Bulletin No. 196: Thromboembolism in Pregnancy. *Obstetrics and gynecology* 2018; **132**(1): e1-e17.
32. Blondon M, Casini A, Hoppe KK, Boehlen F, Righini M, Smith NL. Risks of Venous Thromboembolism After Cesarean Sections: A Meta-Analysis. *Chest* 2016; **150**(3): 572-96.

33. Bain E, Wilson A, Toohar R, Gates S, Davis LJ, Middleton P. Prophylaxis for venous thromboembolic disease in pregnancy and the early postnatal period. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2014; (2): Cd001689.
34. Minig L, Trimble EL, Sarsotti C, Sebastiani MM, Spong CY. Building the Evidence Base for Postoperative and Postpartum Advice. *Obstetrics & Gynecology* 2009; **114**(4): 892-900.
35. ACOG Practice Bulletin No. 210: Fecal Incontinence. *Obstetrics and gynecology* 2019; **133**(4): e260-e73.
36. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. ACOG Committee Opinion No. 736: Optimizing Postpartum Care. *Obstetrics and gynecology* 2018; **131**(5): e140-e50.
37. Macones GA, Caughey AB, Wood SL, et al. Guidelines for postoperative care in cesarean delivery: Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) Society recommendations (part 3). *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* 2019; **221**(3): 247 e1- e9.
38. Wilson RD, Caughey AB, Wood SL, et al. Guidelines for Antenatal and Preoperative care in Cesarean Delivery: Enhanced Recovery After Surgery Society Recommendations (Part 1). *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* 2018; **219**(6): 523 e1- e15.